

Embedding higher order thinking skills in Islamic history (*Sirah*) education in Malaysia

Muhammad Talhah Ajmain@Jima'ain¹, Ahmad Marzuki Mohamed¹, Aminudin Hehsan²,
Aminabibi Saidalvi³, Badlihisam Mohd Nasi¹, Muhammad Sobri Faisal¹, Fareed Awa⁴

¹Islamic Civilization Academy, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Skudai, Malaysia

²Ibnu Sina Institute for Scientific and Industrial Research (ISI-ISIR), Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Skudai, Malaysia

³Academy of Language Studies, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Masai, Malaysia

⁴Academy of Islamic Studies, Universiti Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

The promotion of integrating higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in the Malaysian education system is pivotal to producing analytical thinkers to keep up with the rapid globalization of this era. Thus, the implementation of HOTS in learning and facilitation (PdPc) has been emphasized. However, little is known about the integration of HOTS in Islamic history and civilization (*Sirah*) lessons. Furthermore, teachers continue to use traditional methods and disregard incorporating HOTS in PdPc. Therefore, the current study conducted an in-depth investigation into the components of *Sirah* lessons to support the implementation of the Malaysian education development plan (PPPM) 2013-2015 by strengthening teaching techniques through the use of HOTS for a better understanding of *Sirah* lessons. Using an explanatory sequential mixed method design, the findings reveal that the teaching components of *Sirah* lessons with the integration of HOTS are at a moderate level in the conclusion stage of a lesson. Therefore, the current study proposes a model that integrates HOTS, i.e., the element of attitude, preparation and planning, teaching aids with relevant aspects of PAK21, knowledge of HOTS, mastery of the subject content, teaching techniques and approach, assessment, and evaluation.

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Corresponding Author:

Muhammad Talhah Ajmain@Jima'ain

Islamic Civilization Academy, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia

81310 UTM, Skudai, Johor Bahru, Malaysia

Email: muhammadtalhah.j@utm.my

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of teaching and learning Islamic history and civilization (*Sirah*) lessons has to be emphasized for students to grasp current concerns related to the history of Islam and to have a practical impact on students' daily lives. However, according to Effindi [1], given the present growth of the Malaysian Education curriculum, which includes the integration of higher order thinking skills (HOTS), the pedagogy of *Sirah* lessons has to be re-examined. This is based on the Bloom [2], Anderson and Krathwohl [3] taxonomy model, which focuses on the abilities of the students to analyze, integrate, and translate knowledge of their experiences. Furthermore, transferring classroom learning to real-life applications should be coordinated with the different learning styles of the university students [4]–[7].

However, the integration of HOTS necessitates knowledge, comprehension, and the ability to transfer the functions of cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor elements through teachers' and students' teaching and facilitation also known learning and facilitation (PdPc) practices. Learning *Sirah* lessons is

expected to develop students' thinking and produce students who appreciate, practice, and contribute to religion, society, and country beyond class time. Thus, Islamic education teachers as known *Guru Pendidikan Islam* (GPI) play a critical role in integrating *Sirah* lessons with HOTS in PdPc since *Sirah*, by its very nature, affects one's appreciation of life [1], [8]. Furthermore, this has been emphasized in the Malaysia education development plan 2013-2025.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive and systematic process of using one's intelligence, especially among students, can ensure confidence and appreciation of *Sirah* lesson. In addition to Bloom's taxonomy [2] and Anderson and Krathwohl [3] theories of HOTS, Islamic scholars such as Khaldun [9] classified a person's intellect into four primary levels, namely *tamyizi*, *tajribi*, *nazori*, and *insaniyah nature*, which play significant roles in setting a person's lives [10], [11]. The goal of teaching *Sirah* lessons at the secondary school level, based on Circular No. 11, is to understand the *Sirah* of Rasulullah SAW in Mecca, Madinah, and the contribution of Khulafa' ar-Rashidin, from which lessons can be extracted and applied in daily lives of the students [5]. As a result, the GPI must adopt effective instructions [5], [12]–[14]. This could be done by integrating HOTS into *Sirah* lessons [15]–[17].

The main issue from previous studies is the inconsistent and weak implementation of the HOTS components in *Sirah* lessons. According to previous studies [18], [19], the pedagogy of GPI is still traditional, and thus the implementation of HOTS components is still unsuccessful. In another study, it was found that, despite preparation, teachers' instruction using HOTS in PdPc was inconsistent, with examples that were less relevant and did not correspond to current reality [20]–[24]. Furthermore, there is a lack of methodological structure for the teaching components, i.e., the introduction, development, and conclusion of a lesson [23], [25]–[30]. Plus, the impact of inconsistent teaching problems, lack of lesson planning and preparation, and teacher-centered teaching methods create constraints on students' understanding, loss of focus for learning, and static student knowledge structure [31]–[36].

Based on the issues stated, there are flaws in the execution of GPI pedagogy, which cause adverse effects on students' learning of *Sirah* lessons. Besides, a few studies analyzed the components of a lesson, which include the introduction, development, and conclusion of a lesson with the integration of HOTS in *Sirah* lessons. This is critical in determining the extent to which the HOTS components have been applied throughout the learning and facilitating (PdPc) to address difficulties highlighted by previous studies [37]. Therefore, there is a need for a comprehensive and in-depth study involving GPI and the teaching components of *Sirah* lessons in the conclusion of a lesson that integrates HOTS, especially at the secondary school level.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

Based on the guidelines from previous researchers [38]–[40], this study utilizes an explanatory sequential mixed method research design with a 70% quantitative and a 30% qualitative approach. Questionnaires, interviews, observations, and document analysis were used to collect data. Quantitative methods are used as the first phase of the investigation to identify the structure of the teaching components (introduction, development, and conclusion of a lesson). Once the stages of teaching components are identified, a qualitative investigation of factors that influence the findings was conducted to gather more in-depth and comprehensive data to develop a model of the conclusion components of *Sirah* lesson that integrates HOTS [11], [21], [41]–[43]. Participants in the first phase of the data collection stage were 406 teachers, and later five outstanding GPI were selected. Figure 1 presents the two phases of data collection adapted from previous studies [39], [42], [44].

Figure 1. Explanatory sequential mixed method research design

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The objective of the current study was to identify the implementation of the conclusion components for the *Sirah* lesson that integrates HOTS. Data was collected through a set of questionnaires distributed to all GPIs. The instrument was divided into three sections: a reflection of lesson objectives, a summary of lesson content, and an assessment of students' understanding. However, this study focused only on the reflection of lesson objectives that integrate HOTS.

4.1. Lesson objectives integrating HOTS

Table 1 presents the findings for the reflections of lesson objectives that integrate HOTS. All items were recorded a medium high and medium values. The results showed that all items analyzed in detail recorded mean score in the highest order were item d02 (min=4.00; sp=.742), d05 (min=3.92; sp=.775), d06 (min=3.91; sp=.773), d04 (min=3.58; sp=.871), d03 (min=3.47; sp=.901), and d01 (min=3.19; sp=1.039).

In summary, the descriptive analysis of the lesson objectives reflection highlights that teachers verbally review lesson objectives at the end of the lesson. The reflection approach focused on interaction with students, stating justification, and relating to daily activities. However, writing reflections in a book and asking students to give reasons for each reflection produced in the *Sirah* lesson is still poorly implemented since findings show a moderate mean score level (3.68), which may be due to time constraints.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of the implementation of lesson objectives that integrates HOTS in a secondary school *Sirah* education

Item	Description	Mode and percentage					Min	S. P	Int
		TP (%)	JJ (%)	KK (%)	K (%)	SK (%)			
D01	I ask students to write a reflection on the <i>Sirah</i> lesson in the book	28 (6.9)	67 (16.5)	146 (36.0)	129 (31.8)	36 (8.9)	3.19	1.039	S
D02	I interact with students to achieve the objectives of the <i>Sirah</i> lesson	1 (0.2)	13 (3.2)	67 (16.5)	230 (56.7)	95 (23.4)	4.00	.742	ST
D03	I ask students to give reasons for each reflection generated from the <i>Sirah</i> lesson.	10 (2.5)	48 (11.8)	127 (31.3)	185 (45.6)	36 (8.9)	3.47	.901	S
D04	I asked students to self-reflect on what was learnt from the <i>Sirah</i> lesson and relate it to their daily behavior	5 (1.2)	41 (10.1)	122 (30.0)	190 (46.8)	48 (11.8)	3.58	.871	ST
D05	At the end of the <i>Sirah</i> lesson, I execute the reflection of the lesson objective that has been set	2 (0.5)	16 (3.9)	80 (19.7)	224 (55.2)	84 (20.7)	3.92	.775	ST
D06	I execute reflection verbally during the <i>Sirah</i> lesson	3 (0.7)	13 (3.2)	83 (20.4)	224 (55.2)	83 (20.4)	3.91	.773	ST
Total min							3.68		ST

4.2. Descriptive analysis of the overall implementation of the conclusion component in the secondary school *Sirah* lesson

Overall, the findings for implementing the conclusion component that integrates HOTS recorded moderately high (mean=3.83). The findings for the integration of HOTS or teaching elements revealed that all three components; reflecting on lesson objectives (mean=3.68), summarizing the content of the lesson (mean=3.82), and assessing students' understanding (mean=3.99), all show a pattern of implementation at a moderate to a high level. In sum, the descriptive analysis for all the three elements in the conclusion of a lesson that integrates HOTS is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of the overall mean score and percentage for the implementation of conclusion component that integrates HOTS in secondary school *Sirah* lesson

Item	Description conclusion component	Mode	Variance	Min	Int
D01	Conduct reflection of a lesson that integrates HOTS	406	0.733	3.68	ST
D02	Formulate teaching content that integrates HOTS	406	0.578	3.82	ST
D03	Assess students' understanding of integrating HOTS	406	0.496	3.99	ST
	Close lesson by integrating HOTS	406	0.601	3.83	ST

The results showed that the conclusion component of the *Sirah* lesson is at a moderate-high level. Therefore, the need for researchers to conduct an in-depth and comprehensive study using qualitative methods is necessary. Besides, the extent and reasons for the conclusion of a lesson were recorded as moderately high, which affects the overall implementation of lesson components integrating HOTS needs

further explanation. The researcher selected five outstanding Islamic education (GCPI) teachers as the study sample. Table 3 presents the themes retrieved from the qualitative data, which was later used to develop a model integrating HOTS in the conclusion stage of the *Sirah* lesson.

Table 3. Element model themes influencing the implementation of conclusion component integrating HOTS by GCPI

Themes and codes	Implementation of integration HOTS		Mode				
	Sub-themes and codes		GCPI01	GCPI02	GCPI03	GCPI04	GCPI05
Elements that contribute to the implementation of the conclusion component	Attitude		/	/	/	/	/
	Preparation and planning		/	/	/	/	/
	HOTS knowledge		/	/	/	/	/
	Mastery of contents		/	/	/	/	/
	Teaching aid (BBM)		/	/	/	/	/
	Approach, method, and techniques		/	/	/	/	/
	Evaluation		/	/	/	/	/
	Reinforcement		/	/	/	/	/
	Time management			/			
Ideas					/		

The eight main elements that form the theme to develop a model for the implementation of the conclusion of a lesson that integrates HOTS based on GCPI observations are shown in Figure 2. This includes attitude, preparation, planning, HOTS knowledge, content mastery, teaching aid, methodological and technical approaches, evaluation, and reinforcement. Elements of this model were identified through observations, interviews, and document analysis.

Figure 2. Integration model of HOTS in the conclusion stage of *Sirah* lesson

The findings of the current study are consistent with previous studies [45]–[47], emphasizing the importance of a conclusion component for systematic and effective teaching. This also strengthens the notion that the final stage of a lesson is a critical phase in ensuring the effectiveness of teaching strategies. Furthermore, the findings of this construct also confirm the theory by Al-Qabisi [48] that teachers should reflect on their teaching by reflecting on student achievement and personality based on the PdPc structure from the beginning of the lesson.

The discussions related to the reflection of lesson objective items that integrate HOTS recorded a scale of moderately high level (mean 3.68). This can be explained through a simple implementation focusing on the

verbal method and the existing syllabus. However, several researchers [32], [49]–[51] argued that this type of reflection is usually implemented at the closure of a lesson to encapsulate the entire concept, principles, and ideas of the lesson content. This ensures students understand the integration between the concepts, principles, and impact of *Sirah* lesson on their lives.

The descriptive findings are in line with previous researchers [32], [49]–[51]. It was highlighted that teaching and learning require continuous interaction between teachers and students, especially at the conclusion stage, where teachers will gauge the extent to which the lesson objectives have been achieved. Moreover, teachers' method of measuring student reflection is consistent with the learning model [52]–[54] who highlighted the need to recall and summarize what had been learned from the beginning of the lesson.

The findings for the conclusion of a lesson component show a moderate implementation pattern which led the researcher to investigate the factors through the interview, observation, and document analysis. The findings suggest that the attitude of teachers, lesson preparation and planning, knowledge of HOTS and mastery of lesson content, teaching aids, approach, assessments, and implementation are the challenges teachers face to achieve the lesson objectives. This investigation approach is similar to previous study [41] who highlighted that implementing lesson reflection requires adequate preparation to ensure that it aligns with lesson objectives.

The reflection of lesson objectives needs to be further strengthened by integrating HOTS. Besides, teachers need to interact with students to achieve the *Sirah* lesson objectives and allow students to self-reflect by relating what has been learnt from *Sirah* lessons to their daily behavior. To reiterate, it is crucial to reflect on the lesson objectives by verbally asking students based on the suitability of the topic and the current situation. From the current context, this study meets the recommendations put forward by the Ministry of Education (MoE) through the 21st century standard practice of teaching criteria. This criterion places the need for students to give proactive feedback on what has been learned without relying entirely on explanations from teachers. Furthermore, the integration between the objectives and the implementation of teaching can be translated by formulating lesson content, whether teacher or student-oriented. In summary, the lesson objectives that integrate HOTS are reflected in Table 4.

Table 4. Implementation of objective reflection (RO) integrate HOTS

OP implementation	Level of intellect based on Ibn Khaldun	The Integration of HOTS in OP	Improvement
Verbal reflections on lesson objectives are implemented based on the syllabus and presented at the closure of a lesson. This is conducted with the teacher delivering information without involving student activities.	<i>Aql' Tamyiz</i> <i>Aql' Tajribi</i> <i>Aql' Nazori</i> <i>Insaniyah reality</i>	Reflection is implemented based on the need. Its implementation is through interaction between teachers and students to expand the idea thoroughly.	Teachers need to improve readiness, especially on the content of the lesson objectives and how to adapt the objectives in daily life. The elements of knowledge, commitment, and skills by GPI determine the quality of the reflection.

5. CONCLUSION

The implementation of HOTS focusing on the classroom PdPc and the components of a lesson was initiated in Malaysia back in 2013. However, very few studies were conducted in the field of *Sirah*. Thus, the current study investigated in-depth research on the components of the *Sirah* lesson to help the MoE to add value to the implementation of the Malaysian Education Development Plan (PPPM) 2013-2015 and improve the teaching methods with the integration of HOTS.

The findings highlighted that the teaching component of the *Sirah* lesson is still at a moderate level, although the implementation of HOTS started long ago. Thus, this study provides a guideline to help GPI teach *Sirah* lessons by integrating HOTS elements, i.e., attitude, preparation and planning, teaching aids with selective PAK21 aspects, knowledge of HOTS, and mastery of lesson content, methods and techniques, assessment, and reinforcement. In addition, the current study suggests further investigation into the other components of the *Sirah* lesson, i.e., the introduction and the development stage, to help GPI produce students who can relate *Sirah* lessons as an example or model to face the current reality successfully.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. H. Effindi, "VTA-TJS: Membantu meningkatkan kemahiran mengingat Sirah Nabi Muhammad SAW pemimpin Agung," (in Malay), *Jurnal Pendidikan Islam Kontemporari*, vol. 1, pp. 50–59, 2018.
- [2] B. S. Bloom, *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives*. Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon, Pearson Education, 1956.
- [3] L. W. Anderson and D. R. Krathwohl, *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. Harlow, United Kingdom: Longman, 2001.
- [4] Z. Ramdzan, *Kesediaan, amalan dan strategi pengajaran pendidikan islam kurikulum standard sekolah rendah tahun satu*. Johor Bahru, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (in Malay), 2013.
- [5] Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia (KPM), *Buku penerangan pelaksanaan kemahiran berfikir aras Tinggi (KBAT)*. Putrajaya: Pusat Perkembangan Kurikulum (in Malay), 2010.
- [6] N. Alimom and N. A. M. Azlan, "Koswer pembelajaran interaktif dalam kalangan pelajar sekolah menengah: Penceritaan Khulafa Al-Rasyidin," (in Malay), *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 2289–9855, 2019.
- [7] F. M. Reimers, *Implementing deeper learning and 21st century education reforms: Building an education renaissance after a global pandemic*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-57039-2.
- [8] N. Zakaria, W. N. A. B. W. M. Suhaimi, A. B. B. A. Samah, and N. E. B. M. Asri, "Keberkesanan mata pelajaran Sirah Rasul di sekolah rendah islam (SRI) Ikram Musleh: Satu tinjauan di Negeri Sembilan," (in Malay), *Journal of Hadith Studies*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 77–84, 2019, doi: 10.33102/johs.v4i2.89.
- [9] I. Khaldun, *Muqaddimah Ibn Khaldun*. Kuala Lumpur: Dewan Bahasa Dan Pustaka, 1993.
- [10] M. T. A. Jima'ain and A. M. Mohamad, "Konsep kemahiran berfikir aras tinggi (KBAT) menurut Ibnu Khaldun dalam konteks pengajaran dan pemuahcaraan (PdPc)," (in Malay), *Jurnal Dunia Pendidikan*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 146–157, 2020.
- [11] M. S. Othman, "Komposisi guru pendidikan agama Islam bidang ibadah di Malaysia," (in Malay), Doctoral Thesis, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Ismail (UPSI), 2018.
- [12] A. N. 'Ulwān, *Education of Children in Islam*. Singapura: Pustaka Nasional Pte. Ltd., 2002.
- [13] C. K. C. Kamaruzaman, M. F. M. Yaakob, and H. Awang, "Tahap dan perasaan ketika penyediaan pengajaran guru: Kajian di Sekolah Agama Yayasan Islam Kelantan," (in Malay), *Journal of Educational Research and Indigenous Studies*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2019.
- [14] M. Assalihee and Y. Boonsuk, "Teaching management strategies on 21st century Islamic education for Southernmost Thai Private Islamic Schools," *Anatolian Journal of Education*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 13–28, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.29333/aje.2023.812a.
- [15] W. A. W. Ismail, W. I. Muhammad, M. A. Lubis, and M. I. Hamzah, "Kesediaan guru pendidikan Islam sekolah rendah di Selangor terhadap penerapan KBAT dalam pengajaran dan pembelajaran," (in Malay), *Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Sciences and Engineering Technology*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 79–92, 2016.
- [16] T. N. H. T. Jamil, H. A. Khafidz, and K. Osman, "Strategi guru pendidikan Islam sebagai pendakwah dalam melahirkan pelajar berfikir aras tinggi," (in Malay), *Journal of Islamic, Social, Economics and Development (JISED)*, vol. 4, no. 19, pp. 97–107, 2019.
- [17] M. T. A. Jima'ain and A. M. Mohamad, "Sikap guru pendidikan Islam terhadap penerapan Kemahiran Berfikir Aras Tinggi (KBAT) dalam Pengajaran dan Pemuahcaraan (PdPc)," (in Malay), *e-Journal of Islamic Thought and Understanding (e-JITU)*, vol. 2, pp. 71–82, 2020.
- [18] M. N. Abdullah, "Amalan pengajaran tilawah al-Quran berkesan dalam kalangan guru pendidikan Islam," (in Malay), Doctoral Thesis, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, 2018.
- [19] T. N. H. T. Jamil, H. A. Khafidz, and K. Osman, "Kemahiran berfikir aras tinggi melalui pendekatan tadzakkur," (in Malay), *'Abqari Journal*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 33–45, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.33102/bqari.vol19.3.
- [20] A. M. Ismail, "Pengaruh akidah terhadap penghayatan akhlak pelajar-pelajar sekolah menengah kebangsaan di Malaysia," (in Malay), Doctoral Thesis, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2009.
- [21] A. Y. Kasim and A. H. Tamuri, "Pengetahuan pedagogikal kandungan (PPK) pengajaran akidah: Kajian kes guru cemerlang pendidikan Islam," (in Malay), *Journal of Islamic and Arabic Education*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 13–30, 2010, [Online]. Available: <http://www.ukm.my/jiae/pdf/17.pdf>
- [22] Z. Abdullah, "Pengajaran dan pembelajaran berasaskan pendekatan berpusatkan pelajar dalam Pendidikan Islam di sekolah menengah kebangsaan," (in Malay), Doctoral Thesis, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2012.
- [23] M. F. Ali, "Kompetensi profesional guru-guru sejarah sekolah menengah di Malaysia," (in Malay), Doctoral Thesis, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2017.
- [24] J. Hui, Y. Zhou, M. Oubibi, W. Di, L. Zhang, and S. Zhang, "Research on art teaching practice supported by virtual reality (VR) technology in the primary schools," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 1246, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14031246.
- [25] A. H. Tamuri, M. F. Ismail, and K. A. Jasmi, "Komponen asas untuk latihan guru pendidikan Islam," (in Malay), *Global Journal Al Thaqafah*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 53–63, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.7187/GJAT232012.02.02.
- [26] P. Arbain, "Eksplorasi pelaksanaan pengajaran tilawah al-Quran program j-Qaf dan hubungannya dengan pencapaian murid," (in Malay), Ph.D. dissertation, Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, 2015.
- [27] M. S. Othman and A. Y. Kassim, "Pelaksanaan amalan pengajaran guru pendidikan Islam sekolah menerusi kaedah penyediaan berdasarkan Kemahiran Berfikir Aras Tinggi (KBAT)," (in Malay), *Journal of Advanced Research in Social and Behavioural Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2017.
- [28] N. H. Hussin, "Pengajaran ibadat dalam kalangan guru cemerlang pendidikan Islam," (in Malay), Ph.D. dissertation, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2017.
- [29] F. A. M. Sabri, "Penggunaan kemahiran membuat penutup dalam pengajaran dan pembelajaran," (in Malay), *Asian Education Action Research Journal (AEARJ)*, vol. 8, pp. 9–16, 2021.
- [30] M. T. Jima'ain, N. A. A. Rahman, K. A. Razak, A. M. Mohamad, and A. Hehsan, "Pilot study and data examination for the teaching composition of higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in the field of Sirah on Islamic education teachers," *Jurnal Ilmiah Peuradeun*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 613–628, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.26811/peuradeun.v10i3.694.
- [31] A. H. Tamuri and M. K. A. Ajuhary, "Amalan pengajaran guru pendidikan islam berkesan berteraskan konsep mu'allim," (in Malay), *Journal of Islamic and Arabic Education*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 43–56, 2010.
- [32] Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia, *Buku dasar elemen kemahiran berfikir aras tinggi (Pedagogi)*. Putrajaya: Bahagian Pembangunan Kurikulum (in Malay), 2014.
- [33] N. M. Zhaffar, "Kefahaman dan amalan penerapan pemikiran kritis dalam pengajaran pendidikan Islam sekolah menengah," (in Malay), Ph.D. dissertation, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2017.
- [34] A. R. Azlina, "Kesan kaedah flipped classroom menerusi pembelajaran berasaskan projek ke atas pencapaian dan gaya pembelajaran pelajar," (in Malay), Ph.D. dissertation, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, 2017.

- [35] C. Masingan and S. Sharif, "Pengetahuan pedagogi kandungan (PPK) guru bukan pengkhususan reka bentuk dan teknologi (RBT) di sekolah menengah," (in Malay), *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 64–71, 2019, doi: 10.47405/mjssh.v4i6.279.
- [36] E. S. Mokhtar, N. A. Rosley, S. Z. Ahmad, J. Aurani, and N. M. Saraf, "Multimedia approach (Geo-Sirah) development on Sirah learning with geography elements: primary school students," *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 230–240, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.6007/IJARPEd/v12-i1/16129.
- [37] S. Nachiappan, A. A. Damahuri, C. Ganaprakasam, and S. Suffian, "Application of higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in teaching and learning through communication component and spiritual, attitudes and values component in preschool," *Southeast Asia Early Childhood Journal*, vol. 7, pp. 24–32, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.37134/saecj.vol7.3.2018.
- [38] J. Hair, R. E. Anderson, W. C. Black, and B. J. Babin, *Multivariate data analysis*, 7th ed. Prentice Hall, 2010.
- [39] J. M. Morse, "Molding qualitative health research," *Qualitative Health Research*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 1019–1021, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1177/1049732311404706.
- [40] J. W. Creswell, *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*, 4th ed. Pearson Education Inc, 2012.
- [41] K. A. Jasmi, "Guru cemerlang pendidikan islam sekolah menengah di Malaysia: Satu kajian kes," (in Malay), Ph.D. dissertation, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 2010.
- [42] J. W. Creswell and V. L. P. Clark, *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*, 2nd ed. SAGE Publications, 2011.
- [43] H. Ishak, A. H. Tamuri, R. A. Majid, and S. Bari, "Amalan pengajaran guru dalam pengajaran dan pembelajaran pendidikan Islam di Sekolah Kebangsaan Pendidikan Khas (masalah pendengaran)," (in Malay), *Journal of Islamic and Arabic Education*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 11–24, 2012.
- [44] A. Tashakkori and C. Teddlie, *Handbook of mixed methods in social & behavioral research*. SAGE Publications, 2003.
- [45] G. R. Lefrancois, *Psychology for teaching*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Publishing, 1997.
- [46] R. Ya, Ab. H. Tamuri, M. H. Mohamad, M. M. Mustapha, and K. N. Abd Rahim, "Innovation in Islamic Education BBM (Bulletin Board System) Based on 'Facebook'," paper presented at the *Prosiding Seminar Antarabangsa Perguruan dan Pendidikan Islam (SEAPPI2012)*, Johor Bahru, 2012.
- [47] R. B. Ishak, M. F. B. A. Ghani, and S. Siraj, "Amalan pembelajaran dalam kalangan guru sekolah berprestasi tinggi," (in Malay), *JuKu: Jurnal Kurikulum & Pengajaran Asia Pasifik*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 52–60, 2017.
- [48] A. H. A. M. K. Al-Qabisi, *Al-Risalah al-Mufassalah li-Ahwal al-Muta'allimin wa'l-Muta'allimin*. Tunis: asy-Syirkah al-Tunisiyyah li at-Tauzi, 1986.
- [49] M. Kuipers, F. Meijers, and C. Gundy, "The relationship between learning environment and career competencies of students in vocational education," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 21–30, Feb. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2010.05.005.
- [50] E. Sulaiman, *Pengenalan pedagogi*. Skudai: Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (in Malay), 2004.
- [51] R. M. Nor, N. M. R. B. N. Yusoff, and H. bin Haron, "Meneroka kaedah pengajaran guru cemerlang pendidikan seni visual Selangor (GCPVS): Satu kajian kes," (in Malay), *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (MJSSH)*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 125–140, May 2020, doi: 10.47405/mjssh.v5i5.394.
- [52] R. Glaser and J. Lompscher, *Cognitive and motivational aspects of instruction: Selected International Congress papers*. Amsterdam: Elsevier Science Ltd, 1983.
- [53] A. H. Fadzilah, "Pelaksanaan pengajaran dan pembelajaran koperatif berasaskan abad ke-21: Satu tinjauan di Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Pekan Nenas," (in Malay), Undergraduate thesis, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, 2017.
- [54] J. Dunlosky, K. A. Rawson, E. J. Marsh, M. J. Nathan, and D. T. Willingham, "Improving students' learning with effective learning techniques," *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 4–58, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1177/1529100612453266.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Muhammad Talhah Ajmain@Jima'ain is a Senior Lecturer at the Academy of Islamic Civilization, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM). He received his PhD degree in Islamic Education from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. He was passionate about raising the quality of teaching and learning of teacher and students and their development in the schools. Dr Talhah research interests in the teacher education, Islamic education, Sirah Education, 21st Century teaching and learning, higher order thinking skills (HOTS), classroom research, and youth practices and their education. He can be contacted at: muhammadtalhah.j@utm.my.

Ahmad Marzuki Mohamed received his PhD degree in Educational Management and Administration from Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. He has over 22 years of experience as an academic with Universiti Teknologi Malaysia. A Senior lecturer of the Akademi Tamadun Islam, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, his current research interest as well as publication work includes teaching and learning, teacher training, organizational behavior and Islamic leadership. He can be contacted at email: amarzuki@utm.my.

Aminudin Hehsan received the Ph.D. degree in Fiqh Science and M.Sc. in Education Technology from the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM). He is currently a director, center of research for Fiqh science and technology (CFIRST), Ibnu Sina Institute for Scientific and Industrial Research (ISI-ISIR), UTM. He also editorial board member, Journal Sains Humanika (UTM). His current research interest includes teaching and learning at various levels and areas of education also in empowering technology. His publication topics including Islamic education, educational courses, educational institutions, innovation in teaching and facilitation. He can be contacted at email: ahhsan@utm.my.

Aminabibi Saidalvi is a trained and qualified teacher who has 27 years of teaching experience in the field of English Language education at all levels of education. She currently works at the Academy of Language Studies UiTM Johor, Pasir Gudang Campus. Her teaching and research interests include applied linguistics, teaching English as a second language (TESL), online integrated language learning, online classroom interaction analysis, oral communication skills, second language research. His current research interest includes TESL, ELT methodology, online classroom interaction, second language learning and teaching, language and communication, applied linguistics, online learning, technology enhanced learning. She can be contacted at email: aminabibi@uitm.edu.my.

Badlihisam Mohd Nasir is currently a Professor at the Academy of Islamic Civilization, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM) Johor. He received the Ph.D. degree in the study of the Islamic Movement from the University of Birmingham, UK. Bachelor's degree in the Faculty of Islamic Studies at UKM in Islamic Dakwah and Leadership (1987-1991). He went on to study at the Center for the Study of Islam and Christian-Muslim Relation, University of Birmingham, UK (1993-1998) to get a Master's degree in Christian-Muslim Relations. This academic background forms his main area of expertise as the Dakwah and Islamic organizations, while Islamic Civilization is the focus of both research and teaching. He can be contacted at email: badlihisam@utm.my.

Muhammad Sobri Faisal is a Senior Lecturer at the Academy of Islamic Civilisation, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM). He received his PhD degree in Hadis from Universiti Malaya. His current research interest includes Fiqh hadis, thematic hadis and crime against children. He can be contacted at email: muhammadsobri@utm.my.

Fareed Awae received the Ph.D. degree in Islamic Contemporary Studies of Arabic Education (Curriculum) Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin (UNISZA). He was over 20 years of experience working in education field. He now working as a Senior Lecturer in His research focuses on Arabic education, curriculum, project-based learning, teaching and learning, and Arabic language education. He can be contacted at: fareedo2022@um.edu.my.